

Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Anti-Acne Cream Enriched with Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) Extract

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ABSTRACT

The current study was conducted to develop and evaluate an herbal cream formulation containing tomato extract with other herbal components, namely, aloe vera, neem, turmeric, green tea, cucumber, calendula, and sandalwood oil, for managing acne vulgaris. Acne vulgaris is a prevalent inflammatory skin condition occurring in adolescents and young adults. Herbs are significant for acne management because of their antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidative, and skin-soothing effects with minimal adverse reactions as compared to artificial medicines. Five formulations (F1 to F5) of herb-based creams were developed through the process of emulsion. These formulations were evaluated based on organoleptic parameters, pH value, homogeneity, spreadability, viscosity, washability, extrudability, irritancy, uniformity of drug content, and stability. FTIR and UV-visible spectroscopic methods were used to characterize the developed optimized formulation. F3 had the best physicochemical properties among all formulations, being highly homogeneous with high spreadability (6.7 g·cm/sec), moderate viscosity (16400 cP), high extrudability, and the highest percentage of active ingredient (98.7%). The preparation was compatible with skin pH and non-irritant. No changes occurred after 30 days. FTIR and UV-Vis spectroscopic analysis revealed phenolic compounds, flavonoids, carotenoids, and other bioactive ingredients without chemical compatibility issues. The formulated anti-acne herbal cream was found to be stable, safe, and possessed favorable physicochemical properties. Thus, F3 can be considered as a potential topical treatment for acne patients.

Keywords: Tomato extract, Lycopene, Herbal topical formulation, Phytoconstituents, Antioxidant activity, Anti-inflammatory activity.

INTRODUCTION

Acne vulgaris is an inflammatory condition affecting the pilosebaceous units. It is a common skin condition among teenagers and young adults all over the world. The condition is associated with the development of blackheads, whiteheads, pimples, cysts, and in some instances, permanent scars. Apart from its impact on one's physical appearance, it can have detrimental effects on the individual's psychological well-being. (Ansong et al. 2023). Seborrhea, comedone development, inflammatory alterations, and the proliferation of *Propionibacterium acnes*,

Staphylococcus epidermidis, and *Staphylococcus aureus* in the follicular canal, as well as sebum production, are all symptoms of acne vulgaris, as it is often characterized. It is believed that *Propionibacterium acnes* are obligate anaerobic microbes. By activating complements and by having the ability to convert triglycerides in sebaceous follicles into fatty acids, which chemotactically attracts neutrophils, it aids in the onset of inflammatory acne. In contrast, infections at the sebaceous unit's surface layers are caused by the aerobic bacterium *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. (Charde, Sharma & Avari, J. G. (2014))

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Table. 4 Formula of Herbal Cream formulation

S. No.	Ingredient	Function	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1	Tomato liquid extract	Main active ingredient, Anti-acne	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	7.0
2	Aloe vera liquid extract	Moisturizer	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
3	Neem leaf liquid extract	Antimicrobial agent	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
4	Turmeric liquid extract	Anti-inflammatory agent	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
5	Green tea liquid extract	Antioxidant	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
6	Cucumber liquid extract	Cooling agent	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
7	Calendula liquid extract	Healing agent	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
8	Sandalwood oil	Fragrance and anti-acne agent	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
9	Beeswax	Stiffening agent	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15
10	White paraffin	Emollient base	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
11	Methyl paraben	Preservative	8.0	7.0	6.0	5.0	4.0
12	Distilled water	Vehicle	q.s. to 30 g				

Figure 6. formulation cream F1 ,F2, F3, F4, & F5

5.0 Evaluation Parameter of Herbal Cream

5.1 Physical properties

Morphological evaluation of the prepared herbal anti-acne cream was done in order to determine by the physical and sensory characteristics of the formulation. The criteria for evaluation were the

color, odor, appearance, texture, consistency, of the formulated herbal product. Evaluation of these characteristics plays an important role in assessing quality of the herbal cream formulation.

5.2. PH Determination Parameter

The pH of the prepared herbal anti-acne cream having tomato extract as an active ingredient was measured with a digital pH meter. pH level in topical formulations is a very significant factor as it ensures skin compatibility and prevents skin irritation. The pH level of skin-compatible creams must lie close to the normal skin pH level range.

Procedure of PH Determination

Approximately 1 g of the prepared herbal cream was carefully weighed and then diluted in 10 ml distilled water in a beaker. The mixture was mixed well to obtain a homogenous dispersion. Before performing the measurement, the digital pH meter was calibrated with known buffer solution. The tip of the digital pH meter was dipped into the cream dispersion, and its pH level was measured. The measurement was conducted thrice, and an average reading was calculated.

5.3. Homogeneity

The homogeneity of the prepared herbal anti-acne cream made from tomatoes was determined using visual observation and feel after mixing of the cream. It is important to note that homogeneity is a key factor used to determine the uniform distribution of components in the cream.

Procedure of homogeneity

A little quantity of the prepared herbal cream was then squeezed in-between the thumb and forefinger, and observations were made regarding its uniformity, appearance, and whether there were any aggregates within the formulation.

5.4. Spreadability

The spreadability of the developed herbal anti-acne formulation was measured for testing the ease of application of the cream on the skin. Spreadability is important

because good spreadability allows uniform spreading of the cream on the skin without much friction.

Procedure of Determination of Spreadability

The spreadability of the cream was tested using a little quantity of the cream placed between two glass sheets. The top glass sheet had some weight applied to it, for a fixed duration, to make sure that there was an even spread of the cream between the two glass sheets. After removing the weight on the top glass sheet, some other weight was placed on it and its fall recorded.

Where:

S = Spreadability

M = Weight tied to upper slide

L = Length moved by the glass slide

T = Time taken to separate the slides

$S = \frac{ML}{T}$

5.5. Washability

The washability property of the formulated herbal anti-acne cream investigated to determine the ease with which the cream can be easily removed from the skin surface with the help of water. Washability is a significant property of topical creams.

Procedure of Washability of Herbal Anti-Acne Cream

A small amount of the formulated herbal cream was applied to the skin surface and left to spread evenly. The applied cream was washed with water, and the ease of removal was noted visually and physically.

5.6. Extrudability

Extrudability of the herbal anti-acne cream prepared carried out to check the ability of the cream to come out conveniently when squeezed from a collapsible aluminum tube. It is desirable for easy application of the preparation with minimal pressure required.

Procedure of Determination of Extrudability

Herbal cream was poured in a clean collapsible aluminum tube. The tube was compressed by hand to squeeze out the quantity of the cream. The assessment

was done based on the ease and smoothness of the extrusion process of the cream from the container.

5.7. Irritancy Test

The irritancy test was done on the prepared herbal anti-acne cream to determine whether or not the preparation was safe enough for topical helpfull to the skin. The purpose of conducting the test was to see if there were any symptoms of irritation that were associated with application of the cream to the skin.

Procedure of Irritancy Test

A little quantity of the prepared herbal cream was applied to a small portion of the skin and kept there for a specific period of time. Any symptoms of irritation, such as redness, swelling, itchiness, or rash development, were looked for during the observation process.

5.7. Stability Study

Stability studies were carried out on the herbal anti-acne cream formulation under various storage conditions to determine the physical stability of the formulation. These studies were carried out to determine the changes in the physical attributes such as color, smell, pH, homogeneity, phase separation, and consistency after storage.

Procedure of Stability testing

The herbal formulations for anti-acne cream were filled into suitable airtight containers and stored at different temperature conditions, including normal temperatures and high temperatures, for some time. The physical attributes such as color, smell, pH, consistency, homogeneity, and phase separation were studied.

5.8. Drug Content Uniformity

The uniformity of the content of the drug in the prepared herbal anti-acne cream was done to determine the uniform dispersion of the active ingredients in the cream. This analysis will be useful for determining the consistency of the quality of the prepared cream.

Procedure of Content Uniformity testing

The herbal cream sample used in the experiment weighed 1g. This sample was then diluted in enough solvent, mixed well, and filtered to remove any insoluble substances. After filtration, the absorbance of the resulting solution was measured using a UV-Visible Spectrophotometer.

5.9. Non-Greasiness

Grease level of the prepared herbal anti-acne cream was determined to measure the greasiness of the cream upon application onto the skin. An effective topical cream must impart a smooth sensation without causing excess greasiness on the skin.

Procedure of Non-Greasiness Testing

A tiny amount of the prepared herbal anti-acne cream was applied on the skin surface and then gently rubbed using fingers. The greasiness of the cream was measured after application.

5.10. Moisturizing Property

The moisturizing property of the moisturizing activity of the herbal anti-acne cream prepared by using was assessed to ascertain the extent of its effectiveness in maintaining skin moisture and softness when topically applied on the skin. Moisturizing activity of the preparation is necessary to avoid any skin irritation during the course of acne treatment.

Procedure of Moisturizing testing

An adequate amount of the herbal cream was applied evenly onto the skin surface to absorb entirely into the skin. The effect on the skin was observed in terms of skin texture, softness, hydration, and dryness.

6. RESULT

6.1 Physical Evaluation

These formulated herbal creams have been analyzed in respect to their physical form, color, smell, and texture. These details have been provided in Table 5.

Table.5 Organoleptic Evaluation of Herbal Cream

Parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Color	Light yellow	Pale yellow	Creamish yellow	Light yellow	Yellowish
Odor	Fragrance herbal				
Appearance	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
Texture	Soft	Soft and uniform	Soft and uniform	Slightly thick	Slightly thick
Consistency	Good	Excellent	Excellent	Good	Good

6.2 pH Determination

The pH levels of formulated creams were measured using a digital pH meter. The data is shown below in Table 6.

Table 6. pH of Herbal Cream Formulations

S. No.	Formulation Code	pH Value
1	F1	5.6
2	F2	5.9
3	F3	6.4
4	F4	6.2
5	F5	6.7

6.3 Homogeneity Study

The homogeneity of the formulated creams was visually inspected and tested for consistency. The data is shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Homogeneity Study

S. No.	Formulation	Observation
1	F1	low Homogeneity
2	F2	Good Homogeneity
3	F3	Excellent Homogeneity
4	F4	Good Homogeneity
5	F5	Modrate Homogeneity

6.4 Spreadability Study

Spreadability is one of the most critical factors in topical formulations, as it dictates how easily the formulation can be applied to the skin.

Table. 8 Spreadability of Herbal Cream

S. No.	Formulation	Spreadability
1	F1	5.8 g·cm/sec
2	F2	6.5g·cm/sec
3	F3	6.7g·cm/sec
4	F4	5.7g·cm/sec
5	F5	6.3g·cm/sec

Figure 7. Graph of Spreadability of herbal cream

6.5 Viscosity Determination

The viscosity of cream preparations was measured using a Brookfield viscometer

Table. 9 Viscosity of Herbal Cream Formulations

S. No.	Formulation	Viscosity (cP)
1	F1	14200
2	F2	15800
3	F3	16400
4	F4	17809
5	F5	18200

Figure 8. Graph of viscosity

6.6 Washability Study

Washability was measured using the application of cream on the skin surface followed by washing with water.

Table.10 Washability Study

S. No.	Formulation	Observation
1	F1	Simply Washable
2	F2	Simply Washable
3	F3	Simply Washable
4	F4	Moderately Washable
5	F5	Moderately Washable

6.7 Extrudability Study

The extrudability of the formulations was evaluated based on the ease of extrusion through collapsible tubes.

Table 11. Extrudability of Herbal Cream

S. No.	Formulation	Extrudability
1	F1	Good
2	F2	Good
3	F3	Superb
4	F4	Good
5	F5	Moderate

6.8 Irritancy Test

Application of the prepared formulations on the skin did not show any sign of inflammation, itching, irritation, or redness.

Table.12 Irritancy Test study

S. No.	Formulation	Redness	Irritation	Swelling
1	F1	No	No	No
2	F2	No	No	No
3	F3	No	No	No
4	F4	No	No	Slight
5	F5	Slight	Slight	Slight

6.9 Drug Content Uniformity

Drug content uniformity test was conducted to determine the uniform dispersion of active ingredients in the formulated cream.

Table. 13 Drug Content Uniformity

S. No.	Formulation	Drug Content (%)
1	F1	96.2
2	F2	97.5
3	F3	98.7
4	F4	97.3
5	F5	97.0

Figure 9. Graph of drug content in formulation

6.10 Stability Study

The optimized formulation was analyzed through a stability study for a duration of one month at room temperature.

Table .14 Stability Study of Optimized from Formulation

Parameters	Initial Observation	After 30 Days
Color	Pinkish Cream	No Change
Odor	Pleasant Herbal	No Change
pH	6.5	6.4
Consistency	Smooth	Smooth
Phase Separation	Absent	Absent

6.11. FTIR Spectral Analysis of F3 Herbal Cream Formulation

In this study, the characterization of functional groups and their compatibility within the optimized F3 herbal cream formulation were analyzed using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. FTIR spectroscopy is a critical analytical method employed in preformulation studies for confirming the existence

of active plant constituents and checking the possibility of chemical reaction among components. In the FTIR spectrum of the F3 herbal cream, there were distinct absorption bands belonging to hydroxyl group, aliphatic hydrocarbon, ester group, aromatic compound, and carbonyl group. These peaks imply that the bioactive groups of the herbal extracts are maintained during the formulation process, and chemical incompatibility has not occurred.

Table.15 Interpretation of FTIR Peaks of F3 Herbal Cream

S. No.	Peak Value (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group	Interpretation
1	3647.3 cm ⁻¹	O–H Stretching	Free hydroxyl group of alcohols and phenolic compounds
2	3563.7 cm ⁻¹	H-bonded O–H Stretching	Presence of polyphenols and herbal constituents
3	2979.7 cm ⁻¹	C–H Stretching	Aliphatic alkane group present in fatty acids and lipids
4	1797.3 cm ⁻¹	C=O Stretching	Ester or carbonyl group present in cream base components
5	1674.3 cm ⁻¹	C=C Stretching	Conjugated alkene group of herbal phytoconstituents
6	1482.8 cm ⁻¹	CH ₂ Bending	Aliphatic hydrocarbon chain vibration
7	1239.5 cm ⁻¹	C–O Stretching	Alcohols, esters, and phenolic compounds
8	1177.3 cm ⁻¹	C–O–C Stretching	Ether linkage and ester functional groups
9	1137.2 cm ⁻¹	C–O Stretching	Secondary alcohols and polysaccharides
10	966.7 cm ⁻¹	=C–H Bending	Trans alkene group of carotenoids
11	878.7 cm ⁻¹	Aromatic C–H Bending	Aromatic ring substitution
12	739.4 cm ⁻¹	C–H Rocking	Long-chain hydrocarbon vibration

Figure 10. FTIR graph F3 Herbal Cream

6.12. UV-visible Spectroscopy Analysis of F3 Herbal Cream

The analysis of the F3 herbal cream formulation through UV-Visible spectrophotometry was conducted in the wavelength range of 200-700 nm to determine the active ingredients present within. Three distinct absorptions were noted that confirm the presence of the bioactive ingredients in the sample. First was a prominent peak at 220 nm (1.01 AU), which is indicative of $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ electronic transition and

suggests the presence of phenols and flavonoids responsible for the antioxidant property. Second is the near-UV peak at 336 nm (0.87 AU) suggesting the presence of flavonoids and conjugated phytochemicals responsible for anti-inflammatory effects. Third is a peak at 440 nm (0.97 AU), confirming the presence of carotenoids and natural pigments such as lycopene that absorb in the blue-violet region. These results suggest the successful incorporation of the herbal actives in the formulation and indicate the stability of formulation ingredients.

Table. 16 UV–Visible Spectral Interpretation of F3 Herbal Cream

S. No.	λ_{max} (nm)	Absorbance (AU)	Spectral Region	Possible Phytoconstituent	Interpretation
1	220	1.01	UV Region	Phenolic compounds	Indicates presence of phenols and flavonoids
2	336	0.87	Near-UV Region	Flavonoids / Conjugated compounds	Confirms presence of bioactive herbal constituents
3	440	0.97	Visible Region	Carotenoids / Natural pigments	Indicates presence of chromophoric antioxidant compounds

Figure 11. UV–Visible Spectroscopy graph of F3 Herbal cream

7. DISCUSSION

In the current study, the herbal anti-acne cream was formulated and studied, which included the extract of tomatoes in addition to various herbal components like aloe vera, neem, turmeric, green tea, cucumber, calendula, and sandalwood oil. Herbal formulations have become quite significant in dermatological treatment due to their natural nature, fewer side effects, and improved compliance among patients. Different physicochemical and stability aspects were evaluated for all prepared formulations (F1-F5). It was found that all formulations had good physical appearance, smoothness, and a nice herbal fragrance. Variation was noted with respect to the color and consistency of all formulations because of varying concentrations of herbal extracts used. Among all

formulations, F2 and F3 had better texture and consistency due to effective emulsification. Such results have been recorded before in other studies involving herbal anti-acne cream formulations. For all formulations, the pH range found was between 5.6 and 6.7, which is almost equal to the normal pH of human skin. From this observation, it can be concluded that the formulated cream was non-irritant. The pH value obtained for F3 was 6.4, implying that the product is highly compatible with skin physiology. Regarding homogeneity, it has been determined that F3 showed very good homogeneity compared with other formulations. It should be noted that spreadability and viscosity play an important role in determining patient acceptability and convenience in the application of formulated products. Spreadability test results have shown that F2 and F3

had excellent spreadability. As the amount of herbal extract increases in formulations, the viscosity value has shown a gradual increase up to F5. The optimum viscosity level was obtained in F3. Washability and extrudability tests have shown satisfactory behavior for the prepared formulation creams. F3 exhibited good extrudability and easy washability. Irritancy test findings have shown that formulations F1, F2, and F3 were non-irritant and non-skin irritants; however, F5 was slightly irritant, which may be due to increased active constituent concentrations in the formulation. The drug content analysis revealed that the drug was uniformly distributed among all formulations. F3 showed the highest drug content (98.7%). This suggests efficient mixing of herbal extracts with the cream. One-month stability studies suggested that there were no significant changes in color, odor, consistency, pH, and phases of the optimized formulation, suggesting physical stability of the preparation. FTIR analysis of the optimized F3 formulation revealed the presence of characteristic functional groups like hydroxyl group, carbonyl group, ester, and aromatic group. Lack of any change in peak pattern or absence of any peak in FTIR analysis suggested compatibility of the herbal extract with the excipient. It also suggested the absence of any chemical reaction. UV-visible spectroscopy revealed the presence of phytochemicals in the formulation. Peaks appearing at 220 nm, 336 nm, and 440 nm suggest the presence of phenols, flavonoids, carotenoids, and antioxidants, including lycopene. These phytoconstituents have various medicinal properties, including antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties.

CONCLUSION

The current study has been able to design an anti-acne cream using *Solanum lycopersicum* (tomato) extract along with other herbal ingredients such as Neem, Turmeric, Aloe vera, Green tea, Cucumber, and Calendula. The developed formulation is found to have remarkable antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, soothing, moisturizing, and healing effects, which will be highly advantageous in treating acne vulgaris. FTIR and UV-Visible spectroscopy studies were done in the preformulation stage and revealed the compatibility, stability, and presence of important phytoconstituents without undergoing any

sort of degradation or interaction with each other. Various physicochemical parameters of all formulated creams (F1-F5) were checked out, and F3 proved to be the best among all with appropriate pH, high homogeneity, smoothness of texture, suitable spreadability, ideal viscosity, good extrudability, and cosmetic acceptability. Further, stability and irritancy tests suggested that the formulated cream was stable, safe, and non-irritating for topical use. It is evident from the current study that the formulated polyherbal anti-acne cream has tremendous potential in being used as a safe and cost-effective alternative for treating and managing acne. The use of natural ingredients could minimize the adverse effects of synthetic anti-acne drugs. More research could be done to increase the efficiency and practicality of this formula. Research with human subjects can be done to study its effectiveness in treating acne in humans. There could be more advanced research in terms of phytochemicals and microbial research, which could help to determine the active ingredients of this formula that cause its anti-acne properties. Moreover, mass production, optimization of the formulation process, and addition of preservatives could make the shelf life of the product longer and give it more market value.

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